

Determination of Aluminium in Bauxites and Alloys by Thermal and Fast NAA using $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ Neutron Source

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Two neutron activation analysis methods based on thermal and fast neutron irradiation using $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ source have been suggested for the determination of Al in bauxites and aluminium alloys. The methods induce reactions $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\gamma)^{28}\text{Al}$ and $^{27}\text{Al}(n,p)^{27}\text{Mg}$ from thermal and fast neutrons, respectively. Activities of 1.78 and 0.844 MeV γ -rays were counted on NaI(Tl) detector coupled with a single channel analyser. The results are in good agreement with those from conventional chemical methods. The methods are fast, non-destructive and economic and can be used for the determination of Al in its ores and alloys.

ANALYSIS of geological samples for their elemental composition is one of the most complex problems encountering analytical chemists. Wet chemical and instrumental methods require fusion followed by sophisticated chemical separation schemes which are often tedious and time consuming. During the last two decades several nuclear methods have been developed for the analysis of geological samples^{1,2}. NAA is one of the commonly used method for most elements in different matrices³. Recently, low flux isotopic sources have gained importance in bulk analysis^{4,5}, process control⁶ and mineralogical processes^{2,6}. Gueben *et al.*⁷ first studied the determination of Al by NAA using $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\gamma)^{28}\text{Al}$. Rhodes⁸ has described an on-stream analysis of Al in bauxites Borsaru and Eisler^{9,10} have analysed bulk bauxite and coal samples for their Al content by NAA using isotopic sources. De Weisse *et al.*¹¹ developed a rapid 'automatic bauxite analyzer' and used NAA technique for exploration of lateritic and karstic bauxites from Australia, Philippines, Jamaica *etc.* The results have been compared with those from X-ray fluorescence and found in good agreement. Cyclic activation analysis¹²⁻¹⁴ has been adopted for increasing the accuracy and precision of NAA determination of several elements. Since isotopic neutron sources have low neutron output, it is all the more important for increasing the sensitivity. Recently, some attempts have been made to use fast neutrons (4-6 MeV) from the isotopic sources for the determination of several elements^{15,16}. In the present communication, we report our results on the determination of Al in bauxites and alloys using thermal and fast neutrons from a 5 Ci $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ source. The methods are simple, fast, more economic and non-destructive.

Experimental

Sample preparation and counting: Bauxite samples in powder form (~ 150 mesh), from different parts of India, were dried at $\sim 90^\circ$ for overnight. The Al-metal and alloys were also powdered (~ 150 mesh) in a pulverizer. USGS rock BCR-1 was used as a standard for bauxites and Al metal for alloys. Each of the samples (~ 1 g) of bauxite, alloys and the standard were packed in polythene bags. The samples and the standard were irradiated in a 5 Curie $^{241}\text{Am-Be}$ neutron source (thermal neutron flux $\sim 10^8$ n cm⁻² s⁻¹), obtained from B.A.R.C., Bombay. For thermal neutron irradiation, samples were placed on 2.5 cm paraffin disc¹⁷ and irradiated for 10 min. After a delay of 15 s, 1.78 MeV γ -activity due to ^{28}Al was counted for 4 min. After a further delay of 45 s, sample was reirradiated, delayed and counted in a similar manner and the cycle was repeated 5 times to collect sufficient counts. A pictorial representation¹⁸ of CTNAA is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Timing diagram for cyclic neutron activation analysis: t_0 = cycle starting time, $t_1 - t_0$ = irradiation time, $t_2 - t_1$ = delay time, $t_3 - t_2$ = counting time, $t_4 - t_3$ = return time, $T = t_4 - t_0$ = total cycle time.

For fast neutrons irradiations, samples were kept in a 0.5 mm Cd tray to cut off thermal neutrons¹⁸. Nuclear characteristics¹⁸ and other experimental conditions are given in Table 1. The activity of irradiated samples was counted at the photopeak position on a well type (1.75" × 1.75") NaI(Tl) detector coupled with single channel analyser (ECIL, Hyderabad). About 1000 or more counts were collected in each case and at least three replicate analyses performed. Identification of nuclides was done by characteristic γ -ray spectra and half-life measurements in both cases.

of our method. Another possible interference could be via $^{59}\text{Co}(n, \alpha)^{56}\text{Mn}$ which may be significant depending on the amount of cobalt but its abundance in bauxites is extremely small (<0.003%)²³.

Results and Discussion

Al concentration in bauxite was calculated using U.S.G.S. rock BCR-1 as standard (Al 7.202%)²⁴. It was also intercompared with another local standard, BARC trachyte basalt, TKT-1 (Al-

TABLE 1—NUCLEAR CHARACTERISTICS¹⁸ AND EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS INCLUDING INTERFERENCES IN Al DETERMINATION BY CTNAA AND FNAA METHODS

Nuclear reaction	Half-life $t_{1/2}$, min	Cross-section σ , barn	E_r MeV	Irradiation time min	Delay time s	Counting time min
$^{27}\text{Al}(n, \gamma)^{28}\text{Al}$	2.3	0.235	1.78	10	15	4
$^{27}\text{Al}(n, p)^{27}\text{Mg}$	9.5	0.081	0.844	30	15	5
Interferences				Q. value (MeV)	Abundance in bauxites (%)	
$^{30}\text{Si}(n, \alpha)^{27}\text{Mg}$	9.5	0.046	0.844	-4.19	5-20	
$^{56}\text{Mn}(n, \gamma)^{56}\text{Mn}$	155.0	13.30	0.847	7.27	<0.5	
$^{56}\text{Fe}(n, p)^{56}\text{Mn}$	155.0	0.103	0.847	-2.92	5-15	
$^{59}\text{Co}(n, \alpha)^{56}\text{Mn}$	155.0	0.039	0.847	0.305	<0.003	

Cycle was repeated after 45 s and 5 cycles were used with total cycle period of 75 min

Chemical methods of analysis: The bauxite sample (~400 mg) was fused with NaOH (~2 g) and Na_2CO_3 (~50 mg) in a porcelain crucible. The melt was dissolved in hot 1:1 HCl. Al-metal and alloys were dissolved in concentrated HCl with few drops of concentrated HNO_3 . Al was determined by gravimetric (using oxine reagent¹⁹), volumetric (by adding excess of EDTA and back-titrating with ZnSO_4 using eriochrome black T indicator¹⁹) and spectrophotometric (using aluminon reagent²⁰) methods.

Sources of interferences: In cyclic NAA using thermal neutrons, no other nuclear reactions are expected to be interfere. However, in fast NAA some interferences are expected as listed in Table 1. The first reaction $^{30}\text{Si}(n, \alpha)^{27}\text{Mg}$ producing the same nuclide, not only requires more energetic neutrons (> 4 MeV) but its cross section (0.046 b) and abundance of ^{30}Si (3.10%) are also very small¹⁸. Another possibility of interference could be from 0.847 MeV γ -rays from ^{56}Mn produced by thermal as well as fast neutron reactions. 0.847 MeV γ -rays from ^{56}Mn can not be resolved from 0.844 MeV γ -rays of ^{27}Mg using NaI(Tl) detector²¹. Abundance of Mn in bauxites is extremely small (< 0.5%) and moreover thermal neutrons have already been cut off. Therefore, its contribution is expected to be negligibly small. However, bauxites contain high amount of iron (5-15%)²² and the reaction $^{56}\text{Fe}(n, p)^{56}\text{Mn}$ should be considered. Janghorbani *et al.*²¹ have estimated the amount of interference to be 0.0016 in lunar samples containing 12-16% Fe. Thus, it is very small or below the detection limits

7.96%)²⁵. A mean of 10 analyses of Al in these standards gave 7.20 ± 0.10 and 8.07 ± 0.22 by cyclic TNAA and 7.19 ± 0.11 and 8.08 ± 0.12 by fast NAA respectively. These are in good agreement with the literature values indicating precision and accuracy of the methods. Mean values of three replicate analyses of Al in few representative bauxites and alloys by cyclic thermal NAA and fast NAA and three different chemical methods are given in Tables 2 and 3. Standard deviations for both the methods are ≤ 0.6 . The relative error is estimated to be 2-5%. It is observed that the amount of Al in bauxites and alloys by two NAA methods are in good agreement with those from chemical methods. The overall accuracy of a single determination is better than 0.6% by CTNAA and 0.3% by FNAA methods for bauxites where Al is in the range 15-30%. For alloys containing higher amount of Al it may be still better.

A plot of the amount of Al vs corrected count rate for CTNAA method gave a linear plot (Fig. 2) upto 1.5 g Al. After this, deviations were observed presumably due to self-absorption effects. A similar linear correlation was observed for activity in FNAA method. Figs. 3 and 4 reveal the correlations of results obtained by CTNAA with that of colorimetric method in bauxites, and CTNAA vs FNAA in alloy samples, respectively. Most points fit the linear correlation in confirmation with similar observations by other workers^{9,16}. The data points in Fig. 3 include the analysis of many samples analysed in our laboratory while only few are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Al IN BAUXITES BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Sample* no.	CTNAA %	FNAA %	Gravimetry %	Titrimetry %	Colorimetry %
BGDN-270	26.08±0.40	25.13±0.54	26.86±0.14	26.50±0.22	26.59±0.28
-365	20.74±0.17	20.12±0.20	21.48±0.14	21.55±0.22	21.80±0.17
-489	23.52±0.24	22.63±0.32	23.84±0.45	23.47±0.26	23.53±0.17
-556	25.67±0.17	24.89±0.56	25.35±0.28	25.51±0.14	25.78±0.37
-651	19.53±0.48	19.56±0.30	19.6±0.30	19.74±0.10	19.39±0.41
WCB-691	18.83±0.14	17.79±0.22	18.71±0.20	18.75±0.17	18.82±0.20
-730	23.37±0.17	22.89±0.30	23.55±0.20	23.31±0.17	23.42±0.28
-740	26.46±0.37	25.23±0.35	26.41±0.30	26.53±0.10	26.38±0.46
MC-17	12.40±0.20	11.67±0.10	12.46±0.42	12.79±0.10	12.93±0.20
-18	23.31±0.24	22.90±0.30	23.47±0.20	23.37±0.10	23.34±0.26

* Samples are from eastern (BGDN), Western (WCB) and central (MP) part of India.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Al IN ITS ALLOYS BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Sample	CTNAA %	FNAA %	Gravimetry %	Titrimetry %	Colorimetry %
Al metal	99.92±0.45	99.49±0.50	99.54±0.14	98.56±0.10	98.49±0.45
Al-Fe	82.13±0.48	82.25±0.32	82.78±0.10	82.54±0.26	78.62±0.20
Al-Mg	96.14±0.28	96.56±0.37	95.79±0.42	96.02±0.24	96.02±1.10
Al-Ni	50.21±0.17	49.75±0.14	50.20±0.39	50.55±0.28	49.57±0.28
Al-Cu-Zn	49.86±0.24	49.53±0.36	50.48±0.78	50.01±0.55	49.36±0.26

Fig. 2. Variation of count rate with increasing amount of aluminium in CTNAA method.

Fig. 3. Correlation of Al in bauxites by colorimetric with CTNAA method: (O) CTNAA and (●) colorimetry.

It is observed from Tables 2 and 3 and also from Fig. 4 that the results obtained by FNAA are in general slightly lower than that obtained by CTNAA method. It may possibly be due to small contributions from interferences in the FNAA method. However, FNAA method is likely to yield better results due to better counting statistics as compared

to CTNAA. A minimum of ~ 50 mg or approximately 5% Al in bauxite in a sample size of ~ 1g can be determined using ²⁴¹Am-Be isotopic neutron source of moderate strength. Considering irradiation and counting times, it takes ~ 1.25 h to perform an analysis by CTNAA and only 40 min by FNAA method. This may, however, be reduced

Fig. 4. Correlation of Al determination in alloys by CTNAA method with FNAA : (○) FNAA and (●) CTNAA.

further if several samples are analysed simultaneously. The methods are ideal for process control in aluminium-base industries where rapid and accurate determinations may be required. Recently Holmes *et al.*^{26,27} have developed an on-stream analyser for the simultaneous determination of Al and Fe in ores. Our methods may also be modified for such purposes. Although both NAA methods are fast when compared to chemical or instrumental methods where upto 5 h per sample may be required but FNAA is still faster than CTNAA²⁸.

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